

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE ROLE OF "FATHER" IN THE FAMILIES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH FICTION

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In Uzbek culture, the father is often seen as the head of the family and the primary provider for the household. He is expected to be the authority figure and decision-maker, and his role is often defined by traditional gender roles and expectations. In Uzbek literature, fathers are often portrayed as strong, protective figures who are respected and revered by their children.

In English-speaking cultures, the role of father in families has evolved over time and is influenced by changing societal norms and values. While fathers are still expected to provide for their families, they are also expected to be more involved in their children's lives and take an active role in parenting. In English literature, fathers are often portrayed as complex characters who struggle with balancing their responsibilities as providers with their desire to be present and engaged fathers.

Overall, the role of father in families in Uzbek and English fiction is shaped by cultural and societal norms, as well as individual experiences and perspectives. A comparative analysis of these roles would require a deep understanding of both cultures and their literary traditions.

The attitude reflected in the linguistic image of the world makes it an object of linguistics. In addition, it allows to learn and implement the reflection of family relations in a foreign language. Cross-cultural analysis through the means of linguoculturology, research data were selected from various sources in English and Uzbek languages. Analysis of phraseological units in the English and Uzbek languages allows to identify similarities, differences, uniqueness and originality related to parent-child relationship. The context of this phenomenon includes such concepts as "parents are irreplaceable people", "parental love" and "children's behavior at different ages", "children's associations", etc. creates a clear picture, which is expressed in language that makes enough sense. Exploratory analysis can be used in cross-cultural studies, can be useful for translation classes and further research in this field. Allows you to get acquainted with anthropocentrism specific ethnic culture through language. It is emphasized that the relationship between language and culture is a bridge between a person's worldview, mentality, nationality, national characteristics

and language, because all of them are manifested in the language that a person speaks. Since the anthropocentric orientation in linguistics has attracted the attention of scholars, many studies have been conducted with culture and language as the main topic. Traditions, which are considered an integral part of any national culture, are, as a rule, expressed in the language. Family traditions are an important part of traditions, which are characteristic of the culture of the British and Uzbek peoples. The results of the research show that parental relations reflected in proverbs are vividly expressed cultural characteristics of English and Uzbek family traditions. In order to reveal the similarities, differences and unique features of some family traditions reflected in English and Uzbek linguo-cultural studies, we turned to speech of these languages.

The concept of family traditions includes not only holidays, celebrations and rituals, customs, but also traditional relationships passed from generation to generation. A person's relatives, whether they are near or distant, have a certain thing his place in life. Kinship can be divided into blood relatives and relatives according to the degree of closeness. In this study, we aimed to do a comparative analysis of the relations between this type of relatives in the English and Uzbek languages. Family, families and kinship relations form the culture of the people and show its specific characteristics, and help to realize the national, linguistic image of the world on a large scale. The issue of family relations applies not only to sociology, but also to cultural and linguistic studies. It is natural to approach this problem from the point of view of linguistic and cultural studies. Linguistic units with a cultural-national character attract the attention of researchers with the study of linguistics. Representation of the native speaker's world. Phraseological and paremiological units embodying the national cultural outlook play a cultural role stereotypes. Research requires determining who belongs to the group of blood relatives. Russian linguist, historian says the following classification of blood relatives:

1) Me and my brothers; 2) My father, mother and their descendants; 3) My grandparents and their descendants; 4) My children; 5) All my grandchildren. For children, the family is one of the main places of residence, development and psychological formation. It is a family that creates relationships between family members. Parents are the main sources of interpersonal development for their children (parent-child relationships, parent-ancestor relationships). This issue has attracted attention the attention of many scientists. So what is the relationship between parents and children? The relationship between parents and children is explained by Dunn & Brown. As they noted, this form of

relationship allows the child to understand emotions, because in the conversation when a small child tells his parents about various situations, stories full of joy, surprise and other emotions, emotional speech between parents and children is inevitable. Another scientist says that a sincere conversation in the parent-child relationship guarantees respect, trust and security for the child's psychology. A number of studies have specifically addressed the importance of a parent-child relationship in the family. Despite the love of parents, they need to develop the skills of communicating with children and listening to them. Communication depends on two interlocutors and under no circumstances should Hisham Altalib, Abdul Hamid Abu Sulaiman and Omar Altalib be interrupted. Relationship quality largely depends on parent-child communication, parental feelings of burden Moore, Christine and Busby, Andrea and Bundy, Tawana. Another group of scientists supports the idea that the earlier the parent-child relationship is formed, the more successful the relationship is established, because communication is related to emotional survival, understanding feelings. However, parents differ in the extent to which they discuss feelings with their children. Insecure parents versus secure parents may feel more comfortable discussing positive and negative emotions with their children, and as a result, children of secure parents may have more opportunities to discuss and reflect on feelings. Although most of the work on predicting children's emotion understanding has focused on both parental characteristics such as depression. One longitudinal study provides evidence of a link between parental attachment and children's understanding of emotions.

English and Uzbek languages belong to different language families, and research is not simple. The different culture, mentality, and life experience of these two nations are expressed in language, especially in proverbs. Contrasting and linguocultural analysis of discourses about parent-child relations in English and Uzbek is new for linguistic research, as close studies are conducted to identify culturally specific aspects of the studied issue. English and Uzbek people have different stereotypes about parental relations. These patterns are reflected in the language, especially in proverbs, sayings and idioms. At this point, it makes sense to discuss the possibilities of proverbs as a linguistic phenomenon in revealing the cultural characteristics of a certain ethnic group. In linguistics, the terms comparative and contrastive refer to two different approaches: the first focuses on the similarities between two (or more) sets of objects of the same category, while the contrastive mainly refers to the explanation, study, synchronic plane describe and explain the differences between linguistic

elements. However, in paremiology these terms are often used as synonyms. It should be noted that with comparative, that is, diachronic research, in both linguistics and proverb studies, it is proposed to understand diachronic or historical research, which takes into account the development of the text or the chronological change of some aspects of the proverb. Approaches to the study of parent-child relationships are made from different perspectives, such as psychiatry and psychology. Sociologists, psychologists, sociolinguists and linguists for many years. Based on literary texts, mass communication publications, poems, Lavitsky describes the concept of “Children” of the Vitebsk region of Belarus in his scientific article. It explores children's lives from different perspectives, in which the role and place of parents is inevitable. Go Pintin approaches this issue as a family tradition, comparing Chinese and Russian parentchild relationships based on proverbs and sayings of the two languages. Biktagirova makes a comparative analysis of the issue of the concept of “Family” based on the materials of different languages systematically, such as English, Turkish and other languages.

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